

DESIGNING INNOVATIVE IDEAS IN THE BUILDING MATERIALS PRODUCTION INDUSTRY OF UZBEKISTAN

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O‘ZBEKISTON QURILISH MATERIALLARI ISHLAB CHIQRISH SANOATIDA INNOVATSION G‘OYALARINI LOYIHALASH

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Abstract: *The building materials industry of Uzbekistan has been developing rapidly in recent years and occupies an important place in the country's economy. This thesis analyzes the importance of designing innovative ideas in the building materials industry, existing problems and ways to solve them. The study considers the issues of introducing modern technologies, producing energy-efficient and environmentally friendly products, and expanding the use of local raw materials. It also emphasizes the role of cooperation between research institutes and manufacturing enterprises in implementing innovative projects. The purpose of the thesis is to propose effective innovative approaches for the development of the building materials industry and assess the possibilities of their implementation in practice.*

Keywords: *innovation, building materials, production, industry, technology, energy efficiency, ecology, local raw materials, research, cooperation.*

Annotatsiya: *O‘zbekiston qurilish materiallari ishlab chiqarish sanoati so‘nggi yillarda jadal rivojlanib, mamlakat iqtisodiyotida muhim o‘rin tutmoqda. Ushbu tezisda qurilish materiallari sanoatida innovatsion g‘oyalarni loyihalashning ahamiyati, mavjud muammolar va ularni hal qilish yo‘llari tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda zamonaviy texnologiyalarni joriy etish, energiya tejamkor va ekologik jihatdan xavfsiz mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarish hamda mahalliy xom ashyodan foydalanishni kengaytirish masalalari ko‘rib chiqiladi. Shuningdek, innovatsion loyihalarni amalga oshirishda ilmiy-tadqiqot institutlari va ishlab chiqarish korxonalari o‘rtasidagi hamkorlikning roli ta’kidlanadi. Tezisning maqsadi – qurilish materiallari sanoatini rivojlantirish uchun samarali innovatsion yondashuvlarni taklif qilish va ularni amaliyotga joriy etish imkoniyatlarini baholashdan iborat.*

(2nd international scientific and practical conference)

Kalit so‘zlar: innovatsiya, qurilish materiallari, ishlab chiqarish, sanoat, texnologiya, energiya tejankorlik, ekologiya, mahalliy xomashyo, ilmiy-tadqiqot, hamkorlik.

Аннотация: Промышленность строительных материалов Узбекистана в последние годы развивается быстрыми темпами и играет важную роль в экономике страны. В данной диссертации анализируется важность разработки инновационных идей в отрасли строительных материалов, существующие проблемы и пути их решения. В исследовании будут рассмотрены вопросы внедрения современных технологий, производства энергоэффективной и экологически чистой продукции, расширения использования местного сырья. Подчеркивается также роль сотрудничества научно-исследовательских институтов и производственных предприятий в реализации инновационных проектов. Целью диссертационной работы является предложение эффективных инновационных подходов к развитию промышленности строительных материалов и оценка возможностей их реализации на практике.

Ключевые слова: инновации, строительные материалы, производство, промышленность, технологии, энергоэффективность, экология, местное сырье, исследования, сотрудничество.

The construction industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan is developing rapidly, which is increasing the demand for building materials. Large-scale works in the country, such as housing construction, infrastructure projects and the construction of industrial facilities, require high-quality, affordable and innovative building materials¹. Therefore, the design and implementation of innovative ideas in the building materials industry is becoming an urgent task. This thesis examines the current state of the industry, problems in the introduction of innovations and ways to overcome them. The study pays special attention to the possibilities of using Uzbekistan's natural resources and scientific potential.

Current state of the building materials industry. The building materials industry in Uzbekistan includes more than 13 thousand enterprises². In recent years, the range of products has increased from 120 to 180, which indicates the development of the industry³. Significant progress has been made in the production of cement, drywall, ceramic tiles, glass and other materials. However, import dependence, high energy

¹ Official website of the Ministry of Construction and Housing and Communal Services of the Republic of Uzbekistan. URL: <https://mc.uz>

² "Uzbekistan's Building Materials Industry: Yesterday and Today". Website of the "Uzsanoatqurilishmateriallari" Association. URL: <https://uzsm.uz>

³ "More than 10,000 construction materials manufacturing enterprises operate in Uzbekistan." Daryo.uz information portal. URL: <https://daryo.uz>

consumption and environmental problems are still relevant. For example, although the share of the “dry” method in cement production has reached 80 percent, the widespread introduction of energy-saving technologies is not enough⁴.

The importance of designing innovative ideas. The design of innovative ideas is important for increasing competitiveness, improving product quality and reducing costs in the building materials industry. The production of modern technologies, such as self-healing concrete, energy-saving float glass and composite reinforcement, not only provides the domestic market, but also expands export opportunities. Innovations ensure environmental sustainability by increasing the use of local raw materials (reed, fly ash, graphite) and recycling waste.

Integration of research and production. Cooperation with research institutes and higher education institutions is important for implementing innovative ideas in practice. For example, the Scientific and Technical Council under the “Uzsanoatqurilishmateriallari” Association accepted 31 innovative projects and recommended 7 of them for financing⁵. Projects such as the production of oil-free construction bitumen from gossypol tar and ceramic paints from local waste are opening up new opportunities for the industry⁶. At the same time, the lack of infrastructure and limited financial support for the commercialization of scientific developments remain a problem. There are a number of problems in introducing innovations in the industry:

- Financial constraints: There is not enough public and private sector funds to finance startup projects
- Technological infrastructure: There is a small number of modern laboratories and testing equipment.
- Shortage of qualified personnel: There is not enough specialists to manage innovative projects.

The following are proposed as solutions:

- Studying foreign experience (for example, Japanese asbestos-free slate technology) and adapting it to local conditions⁷.
- Establish research centers and launch more cooperation projects between scientists and enterprises.
- Increase the allocation of preferential loans and grants by the state.

⁴ "The building materials industry is at a new stage of development." Website of the "Uzsanoatqurilishmateriallari" association. URL: <https://uzsm.uz>

⁵ "Innovative building materials are produced." Website of the "Uzsanoatqurilishmateriallari" association. URL: <https://uzsm.uz>

⁶ "How is the building materials industry changing?". Review.uz economic analysis portal. URL: <https://review.uz>

⁷ The building materials industry is developing!". Turonbank official website. URL: <https://turonbank.uz>

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In the construction materials industry of Uzbekistan, the development of innovative ideas is an important factor for the sustainable development of the sector. The study showed that the competitiveness of the industry can be increased by using local raw materials, introducing energy-saving technologies, and developing scientific and practical cooperation. However, in this process, it is necessary to solve financial, technological, and personnel problems. Innovative approaches not only provide the domestic market, but also serve to increase export volumes. The following were offered as suggestions:

- Strengthen state support: Develop a program of special grants and preferential loans for innovative projects.
- Development of foreign cooperation: Studying the experience of leading countries and establishing technology transfer.
- Training: Opening special courses in higher educational institutions in the direction of "Building materials innovation" and improving the skills of specialists.

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